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1. ZAMONAVIY IJTIMOIY VOQE'LIKNING O'ZIGA XOSLIGI VA ZAMONAVIY JAMIYAT DINAMIKASINI ANIQLASH
2. MINTAQAHOLISI QADRIYATLARINING DINAMIKASI
3. MINTAQANING IJTIMOIY-IQTISODIY MAYDONI: AN'ANALAR VA INNOVATSIYALAR
4. ZAMONAVIY DUNYO IJTIMOIY MANZARASINING TRANSFORMATSIYALASHUVI

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SOTSILOGIYA KAFEDRASI
"IJTIMOIY FIKR" RESPUBLIKA JAMOATCHILIK FIKRINI O'RGANISH MARKAZI

ZAMONAVIY DUNYONING IJTIMOIY MANZARASI VA JAMIYAT TUZILMALARI TRANSFORMATSIYASI

xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferentsiyasi
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MAQOLADA KELITIRILGAN DALILLARNING TO'G'RILIGI UCHUN MUALLIF MAS'ULDIR | АВТОР НЕСЕТ ОТВЕТСТВЕННОСТЬ ЗА ДОСТОВЕРНОСТЬ ФАКТОВ ИЗЛОЖЕННЫХ В СТАТЬЕ

mutaxassislarni tayyorlash, “Oliy ta’lim muassasalarini QS va TNE xalqaro reytinglariga kirishi uchun maqsadli dasturi”da belgilab qo’yilgan chora tadbirlar asosida xalqaro akademik mobilligi, Xirsh indeksini oshirish kabi qator amaliy ishlarni boshlab yuborganlar.

Hozirgi vaqtda mamlakatda oliy ta’lim doimiy rivojlanmoqda, siyosat, iqtisodiyot va jamiyatdagi o’zgarishlarga javoban, jamiyatning o’zgaruvchan ehtiyojlariga moslashmoqda, chunki dunyo tez sur’atlar bilan o’zgarib bormoqda, o’zgaruvchan munosabat, qiziqishlar, dunyoqarashlar, bo’lajak kadrlar uchun yangi yuqori darajadagi tayyorgarlikni talab qiladigan texnik ehtiyojlar va x.k. Shunday ekan, hozirgi kunda o’qitiladigan fanlar bo’yicha kompetentsiyaviy yondashuvga asoslangan davlat ta’lim standartlari va o’quv dasturlarini takomillashtirish va amaliyotga joriy etish talab etilmoqda. Bu borada yurtimizda ta’limning uzluksizligi, uzviyligi, ustuvorligidan kelib chiqib kommunikativ kompetentsiya; ijtimoiy faol fuqarolik kompetentsiyasi; milliy va umummadaniy; fan va texnika yangiliklaridan xabardor bo’lish hamda foydalanish kompetentsiyasi; tahlil qilish va baholash kompetentsiyasi; umumiy kasbiy kompetentsiyalarni bo’lg’usi kadrlarda shakllantirish kabi qator masalalar yuzasidan yanada chuqurroq faoliyat olib borilish lozimligi ta’kidlanmoqda.

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SOCIAL CAPITAL AS A FACTOR OF IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF LIFE

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Abstract: The genesis of the emergence of the concept of "social capital" is characterized from the historical and criminological side. The research author puts forward the conclusion that the civilizations of the East and West determine the poles, that is, the main regional and cultural divisions of the world. The peculiar properties of these poles are manifested in various forms of the political system, lifestyle of the population, mentality, and religion.

Keywords: Social capital, strategic SWOT analysis, strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, strategic situation SNW analysis, neutrals.

СОЦИАЛЬНЫЙ КАПИТАЛ КАК ФАКТОР ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КАЧЕСТВА ЖИЗНИ

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Аннотация: Генезис возникновения понятия «социальный капитал» характеризуется с историко-криминологической стороны. Автор исследования выдвигает вывод о том, что цивилизации Востока и Запада определяют полюса, то есть основные регионально-культурные деления мира. Своеобразные свойства этих полюсов проявляются в различных формах политического строя, образе жизни населения, менталитете, религии.

Ключевые слова: социальный капитал, стратегический SWOT- анализ, сильные и слабые стороны, возможности, стратегическая ситуация, SNW-анализ, нейтралы.

Today, on a global scale, the emergence of various methodological approaches to introduce the concept of social capital to improve the quality of life of the population, not only generally recognized approaches in the study of the social capital of the population, but also the problem of using ethno methodological principles that express the socio-cultural properties of any country, are becoming the main and priority social issues. According to the information, "on the map of world countries, if the Kingdom of Denmark ranked 1st among 167 countries in the social capital rating in 2020, then the Republic of Uzbekistan ranks 20th" [1]. In this regard, over the past quarter of a century, the ongoing socio-economic reforms have been much improved, and the need to study social capital in modern conditions is of current importance.

Targeted surveys of social capital are being conducted around the world based on criteria such as personal and social relationships, institutional trust, social norms and citizens' participation in society, in the "Better Life Index" rating studies [2]. Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), in studies within the framework of the programs "Quality-of-life index, where-to-be born index" of the company "Economist Intelligence Unit" and rating studies of the Legatum Institute "The Legatum Prosperity Index TM 2020"[3; 17], the need is put forward a systematic analysis of non-material sources leading to material well-being, based on such spiritual values as friendship, trust, cooperation, social unity, among the people of society.

The reforms carried out in our country, where attention is paid to improving the living standards of the population, are associated with the growth of social incomes of the population, improving the quality of living conditions. "... the effectiveness of the ongoing economic reforms and social transformations will be measured primarily by how much they affect the material well-being of the population, the growth of the level and quality of life." [4; 17] From this point of view, improving the quality of life of the population of our country is determined directly by the relations of people based on sincere trust in each other, cooperation and social unity. Since these relations form the core of the concept of social capital, in the conditions of the country, the study of socio-cultural qualities is of great scientific and practical importance.

This research serves the implementation of the tasks defined in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan. No. ZRU-376 of September 25, 2014 "On social partnership", Decrees and Resolutions

of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP - 4947 of February 7, 2017 "On the Action Strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", No. UP - 5938 of February 18, 2020. "On measures to establish a socio-spiritual atmosphere in society, further support for the mahalla institution, as well as raising the system of work with families and women to a new level", No. PP - 4210 dated February 25, 2015. "On measures to improve the positions of the Republic of Uzbekistan in international ratings and indices", No. PP - 4653 dated March 26, 2020 "On organizing the activities of the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as organizations subordinate to it", as well as in other regulatory - legal documents on the subject.

The problems of improving the quality of life of the population and the relationship of social capital issues have been studied in all periods of human history. Such scientists who formed the theoretical and social conceptual foundations of social capital, when measuring social capital, they proposed an impact on economic development, unit of measurement, combination method of evaluation, indicators of evaluation of social sectors.

Domestic scientists: O.Salimov, K.Kuranboev and A.Kodirov [5, 5], M.Bekmurodov [6, 52], A.Umarov [7, 25], Sh.Sodikova [8, 241], T.Matibaev [9, 123], B.Farfiyev [10, 70-115], M.Ganieva [11, 29], N.Latipova [12, 7], A.Jalilov [13, 112] and S.Saidov [14, 13], [15], [16] - studied friendship, one of the indicators of social capital, communication, which is the basis of social communication, the need to form in the mahalla and family system, social partnership, in the social protection system, contribution to the development of national values, in organizing the foundations of civil society within the framework of political science, interpretation in modern society, studied, within the framework of the quality of life of the population, the economic aspects and factors of social capital as an inseparable part of society.

Fig. 1. Strategic situational SNW analysis of social capital

Along with this, this study simultaneously carried out a strategic situational analysis of social capital - SNW analysis (S-Strength - strengths, N-Neutral - neutrals, W-Weakness - weaknesses). Based on this, one can see the benefits of the strengths of social capital. Strengths mainly manifest themselves in the parameters of the first degree "Indicator of a person's faith in himself and the future", the second degree "Indicator of respect for people and the level of tolerance towards them", the third degree "Indicator of the level of sociability of people". Analyzing these parameters, the researcher, based on the data of national qualities formed among members of society, concludes that many respondents, considering the highest value, noted self-confidence, respect for elders and younger, tolerance regardless of nationality, cooperation with people, partnership activities, and most importantly - this is mutual assistance.

Based on foreign experience, the results of a social empirical study conducted in Uzbek mahallas were reflected at the head to determine the level of units of measurement (indicators) with national properties, social capital. Here, respondents selected from all regions of the country on the basis of a quota filled out anonymous questionnaires aimed at assessing indicators of social capital based on a 10-point Likert scale. The main significance of this study is to study the measurement of social capital on the basis of national properties in the activities of mahallas - the system of self-government, that is, the regional society.

Proposals and a conceptual scientific conclusion were developed on the development and formation of social capital, which serves as a spiritual factor in improving the quality of life of the population of the country's regions, based on the results of a study conducted on the basis of the standards of the international community.

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О‘ЗБЕКИСТОНДА КАМБАҒ‘АЛЛИКНИ ҚИСҚАҚТИРИШНИНГ «UMPR» MODELI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada kambag‘allikni qisqartirishga ko‘maklashuvchi «UMPR» (Uzbek Model for Poverty Reduction) modeli mamlakatda kambag‘allikni qisqartirishga doir ishlarni faollashtirishi va chora tadbirlar intensivligini ta‘minlashi mumkinligi haqida so‘z yuritiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: UMPR, profilaktika, himoyaga muhtoj, ehtiyojmand, mehnat kar‘erasi, funktsiya, iste‘mol.

“UMPR” MODEL OF POVERTY REDUCTION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract : The article talks about the possibility of the "UMPR" (Uzbek Model for Poverty Reduction) model, which helps to reduce poverty, to activate the work on poverty reduction in the country and ensure the intensity of measures .

Keywords: UMPR, prevention, in need of protection, needy, labor career, function, consumption .

Mamlakatda kambag‘allikni qisqartirish siyosati keng qamrovli bo‘lishi zarur. Shuningdek, kambag‘allikni qisqartirishda iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy kambag‘allikni farqlash lozim bo‘ladi. Iqtisodiy kambag‘allikni bartaraf etish uchun davlat tomonidan iqtisodiy chora tadbirlarni qo‘llash orqali qisqartirish mumkin. Ijtimoiy kambag‘allikni qisqartirish uchun esa, aholining daromadlarni qayta taqsimlash imkoniyatiga asoslangan mintaqaga ega bo‘lishi lozim. Hozirgi kunda Yangi O‘zbekistonda kambag‘allikni qisqartirish bo‘yicha davlat siyosatining muvofaqiyatli amalga oshirish uchun «UMPR» (Uzbek Model for Poverty Reduction, Kambag‘allikni qisqartirishning O‘zbek modeli) dasturini amalga oshirishni maqsadga muvofiq deb o‘ylaymiz. Ushbu dasturda uchta asosiy yo‘nalishda kompleks chora tadbirlar amalga oshirish lozim bo‘ladi:

1. Mamlakatda kambag‘allikni yanada kengayib ketishini oldini olish uchun aholi orasida kambag‘allikni profilaktika qiluvchi ishlarini olib borish.

2. Mehnatga layoqatli fuqarolarning mehnat munosabatlarida teng huquqlilik tamoyili asosida ishtirok etish imkoniyatlarini mustahkamlash.

3. Aholining ijtimoiy himoyaga muhtoj va ehtiyojmand qatlamlarini qo‘llab-quvvatlash tizimini doim takomillashtirib borish.

Sanab o‘tilgan ushbu vazifalarni bajarilishini ta‘minlash uchun davlatning iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy siyosatining umumiy yo‘nalishi nuqtai nazaridan amalga oshirilishi lozim bo‘ladi.

«UMPR» modelida O‘zbekistonda kambag‘allikni qisqartirish bo‘yicha kompleks chora-tadbirlarda etakchi rolni profilaktika ishlari egallashi zarur. Kambag‘allikni profilaktikasi amalga oshirish birinchidan, mamlakat iqtisodiyotni barqarorlashtirish va o‘sish uchun qulay bo‘lgan makroiqtisodiy va tarmoq siyosatini amalga oshirish imkonini bersa, ikkinchidan, hududiy va mahalliy darajada qabul qilingan iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy qarorlarni aholi daromadlari dinamikasiga

I-SHO'BA. ZAMONAVIY IJTIMOY VOQELIKNING O'ZIGA XOSLIGI
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